

ECOLOGY OF *HAEMOPIS SANGUISUGA* (LINNAEUS, 1758) - THE LARGE FALSE HORSE LEECH IN THE MIRZACHUL TERRITORY

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Abstract. *Haemopsis sanguisuga*, also known as the large false horse leech, is a predatory and predominantly terrestrial species of leech. In the aquatic ecosystems of the Mirzachul region, this species inhabits stagnant and slow-flowing water bodies, including small lakes and canals. *Haemopsis sanguisuga* plays an important role in regulating populations of small invertebrates, as it feeds mainly on insects, mollusks, and worms, and demonstrates high adaptability to changes in the aquatic environment. In the conditions of Mirzachul, this species is resistant to moderate fluctuations in pH and dissolved oxygen content, which contributes to the stability of its population in the local ecosystem.

Keywords: hydrobiont, environmental factors, temperature, pH, flow rate, biota, eurybiont, stenobiont, dominant, ecosystem, ecological valence, tolerance.

Introduction. *Haemopsis sanguisuga* is an extremely valuable and scientifically significant subject for freshwater ecosystems, as this species performs important ecological functions in the ecosystem of water bodies. Its presence and special role in the food chain serve as a unique indicator for assessing the overall state of aquatic ecosystems. *Haemopsis sanguisuga*, like other freshwater leeches, has the ability to adapt to a wide range of environmental conditions, which allows for an in-depth study of the ecology of water bodies in different geographical zones, such as the Hungry Steppe. The study of the ecological plasticity and functions of this species in the ecosystem creates a solid scientific basis for ensuring the sustainability of the aquatic environment. Thus, the study of the species *Haemopsis sanguisuga* forms the necessary scientific foundation for determining the ecological sustainability of freshwater systems and a comprehensive analysis of their role in the ecosystem.

Hydrobiont, known as *Haemopsis sanguisuga* or commonly as the horse leech, is a permanent inhabitant of freshwater bodies in the Eurasian region. This species, belonging to the family *Haemopidae*, is distinguished by its large size, smooth and even body, as well as its specific coloration, which helps it adapt to the environment. The morphology of *Haemopsis sanguisuga* allows it to move freely underwater and easily glide on the substrate. Regarding its feeding habits, *H. sanguisuga* hunts small invertebrates and some small fish, controlling their numbers and thereby contributing to the maintenance of biological balance.

H. sanguisuga is most commonly found in temperate water bodies of Europe and Asia, including slow-flowing rivers and stagnant swamps. Due to its adaptability, the species can also inhabit water bodies with varying levels of acids and alkalis. Acting as a predator in the freshwater ecosystem, it regulates the populations of invertebrates such as insects and mollusks, contributing to the stability and biodiversity of the ecosystem. Additionally, *H. sanguisuga* serves as food for large fish and other predators, acting as an important link between the trophic levels of water bodies. Its presence indicates the health of the ecosystem and the stable state of water [2, 4, 5, 8].

The unique hydroclimatic conditions of the Hungry Steppe present an interesting natural laboratory for studying *Haemopsis sanguisuga* populations. The water bodies in this area are characterized by significant fluctuations in temperature, pH levels, and mineralization, which create specific opportunities for the adaptation of hydrobionts such as *H. sanguisuga* to high summer temperatures of the Hungry Steppe (up to +40°C), changes in water acidity, high levels of mineralization, and fluctuations in the amount of dissolved oxygen affect the life activities of this species and other aquatic organisms.

Such anthropogenic factors and changes in the natural climate influence the populations of hydrobionts and shape their adaptation strategies. *H. sanguisuga* may exhibit behaviors such as changing feeding habits under stressful conditions, migrating to new habitats, or developing new survival methods. Therefore, studying the population of *Haemopsis sanguisuga* provides information necessary for preserving the state of aquatic ecosystems and their ecological sustainability, especially under conditions of increasing pressure from human activity.

Such anthropogenic factors and changes in natural climate have a direct impact on the population of hydrobionts and lead to the formation of their adaptation strategies. *Haemopsis sanguisuga* can change eating habits in stressful situations, move to new habitats, or develop new self-defense strategies. Therefore, the study of *Haemopsis sanguisuga* populations is of great scientific importance for assessing the overall state of aquatic ecosystems and preserving their ecological stability, which is especially necessary in the context of increasing human activity pressure.

Data collection methods. Sampling methods from the aquatic environment and biota were conducted taking into account seasonal changes throughout the year, which allows obtaining extensive information about the dynamics of the ecosystem. Samples were collected twice a month, especially in spring and autumn, when parameters may change. This methodology allows for a deep study of seasonal and monthly changes in the population of aquatic animals [2,3,6].

The collection and determination of *H. sanguisuga* was carried out according to the Lukin method (1976). To collect *H. sanguisuga*, special traps and nets were used, which were installed at the bottom of water bodies and in the coastal zones. The main collections were conducted in the morning and evening, and the exact identification of the species was determined for freshwater mollusks and other invertebrates using microscopic studies and special identification keys.

Measured parameters. To assess the overall water condition of rivers and reservoirs, the following parameters were measured: the water temperature was within the range of 20-25°C and was measured using a digital thermometer; The pH level ranged from 6.5 to 8.5, which was determined using a portable pH meter; dissolved oxygen content ranged from 6 to 12 mg/l and was measured using an oximeter; water mineralization ranged from 200 to 800 mg/l, which was assessed by laboratory methods. These data are very important for analyzing the quality of the aquatic environment.

Biotic factors - abundance and biomass of *Haemopsis sanguisuga*: This species was observed in the Hungry Steppe territory and quantified based on capture results. To analyze species associations and interactions, a species list was compiled and cases of cohabitation were studied. When assessing diversity based on population indicators, Shannon and Simpson indices were used, which helped determine biological diversity and evenness among species.

The interaction of *Haemopsis sanguisuga* with other aquatic organisms was also considered. In particular, competition or symbiotic relationships with other species inhabiting these biotopes,

including other leech species or mollusks such as *Corbicula fluminalis*, were observed, and the struggle for habitats and resources was analyzed.

Impact on territorial biodiversity: The activity of *Haemopsis sanguisuga* in the Hungry Steppe area can significantly influence local ecological systems and their energy exchange, as well as nutrient cycling.

Water temperature (20-24°C) is optimal for many aquatic organisms, while excessively hot or cold temperatures can lead to stress in this species' population and decrease its numbers. *Haemopsis sanguisuga* is sensitive to temperature fluctuations and can only survive within the optimal range.

Water pH level (6.5-8) is neutral and suitable for most aquatic organisms due to a small amount of hydroxide. Changes in pH, particularly towards acidity, can be dangerous for *Haemopsis sanguisuga*, reducing survival probability, especially given its narrow pH tolerance range.

Mineralization (200-800 mg/l) - soil composition and the amount of salts in the water have positive or negative impacts on the species' existence. If *Haemopsis sanguisuga* has not adapted to high salinity, the population of this species is likely to decline.

Dissolved oxygen (6-12 mg/l) - A high amount of oxygen required for *Haemopsis sanguisuga* metabolism helps maintain the population, while a lack can lead to its decrease.

H. sanguisuga β - α as a mesosaprobic organism depends on average transparency and flow rate. The transparency level directly affects the penetration of sunlight and the photosynthesis processes of aquatic plants. The transparency level has a direct impact on the permeability of solar radiation and the processes of photosynthesis of aquatic plants.

Monitoring climate change and human impacts will be of great importance in studying the ecological significance of *Haemopsis sanguisuga*. Regular observation of these factors for forecasting long-term changes in the ecosystem allows for more accurate conclusions, enriches research results, and serves to broaden the scientific approach.

Studies show that the habitat of *Haemopsis sanguisuga* largely depends on water temperature, oxygen content, flow rate, transparency, and mineralization, which reveals the degree of the species' adaptation to the conditions of the region's water bodies.

The distribution range of hydrobionts in river and canal systems of water bodies in the Mirzachul region has been studied. Results showed a wide ecological distribution of the species *Haemopsis sanguisuga* in rivers such as Syr Darya, Zaminsuv, Sangzor, and Guralash, confirming their high ecological adaptability. However, in canal conditions, this species' distribution was observed to depend on a narrow range of ecological conditions (Table 1). Abiotic factors, particularly water flow velocity, mineralization level, and pH changes in the Southern Mirzachul and Dustlik canals, significantly influenced the species' distribution.

Haemopsis sanguisuga was not found in canals originating from Mirzachul, Jizzakh Main Canal, and Arnasay Reservoir, indicating that the abiotic conditions in these areas are unsuitable for the species' ecology.

These findings emphasize the need for a more comprehensive study of *Haemopsis sanguisuga*'s bioecology. While this species has demonstrated broad adaptation to ecological conditions in the Mirzachul region's rivers, it has a narrow distribution range in canals. When analyzing this population's status, it is crucial to consider the high likelihood that water factors (flow rate, pH, mineralization) affect their abundance and distribution.

Table 1

Distribution and ecological groups of hydrobionts in river and canal populations of the Mirzachul region
(*n* = 10, specimens/m²)

The *Haemopsis sanguisuga* population can be either stable or rapidly changing, depending on the variability of conditions. Therefore, *Haemopsis sanguisuga* can be characterized as a eurybiontic organism with a high level of ecological valence and tolerance.

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